

Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

PREVENT

marine litter derived from fisheries activities.

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

AVOID

loss of fishing gears.

Fishing Gears Location with Acoustic Tags

MITIGATE

harmful impacts of ALDFG.

Detection and Removal of ALDFG

The three NETTAG+ solutions will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries.

PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta)

AVOID

Fishing Gears Location with Acoustic Tags (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Malta, United Kingdom)

MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of ALDFG - Map, Track, Recover (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta)

WORKING DIRECTLY WITH THE FISHING INDUSTRY

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